

Table 1 continued

Host	Parameter								Overall average ranking ^d	
	Nymphal survival (%) ^b		Nymphal duration (d) ^c		Eggs laid (no./5 females)					
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i> (L.) Beauv.	1.0	± 0.2	mn	34.8	± 1.6	l	22.2	± 13.2	k-o	26
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	0		n	0		0	4.3	± 9.3	no	27
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf.	0		n	0		0	65.8	± 10.8	d-h	28
<i>Bambusa</i> sp.	0		n	0		0	21.4	± 10.2	k-o	29
Cyperaceae										
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	30.0	± 14.1	def	27.9	± 1.1	f-h	26.6	± 17.1	j-o	11
<i>C. rotundus</i> L.	18.0	± 15.5	f-j	28.2	± 0.9	f-h	28.0	± 19.1	i-o	17
<i>C. kyllingia</i> Endl.	14.0	± 5.2	h-l	28.3	± 1.4	f-h	43.3	± 19.0	g-m	19
<i>C. difformis</i> L.	8.0	± 6.3	j-n	29.5	± 1.6	h-k	15.8	± 8.9	l-o	20
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.)	3.0	± 2.8	k-n	33.8	± 0.8	kl	36.7	± 23.2	h-n	25
<i>Cyperus brevifolius</i> (Rottb.) Hassk.	27.0	± 16.4	d-g	31.0	± 0.8	i-k	85.8	± 44.1	d	30
Commelinaceae										
<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm. f.	11.0	± 3.2	i-n	28.9	± 0.6	fi	7.8	± 4.7	no	21
<i>Murdannia nudiflora</i> (L.)	0		n	0		0	19.8	± 9.0	k-o	29
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	0		n	0		0	12.4	± 9.6	l-o	33
Leguminosae										
Soybean	1.0	± 0.5	mn	29.7	± 1.1	h-k	18.9	± 17.0	k-o	22
Mungbean	1.0	± 0.7	mn	30.8	± 0.9	i-k	2.1	± 2.6	no	25
Cowpea	0		n	0		0	24.0	± 16.5	k-o	29
Amaranthaceae										
<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	0		n	0		0	30.9	± 16.2	i-o	29
Pontederiaceae										
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl.	0		n	0		0	14.1	± 4.6	l-o	32
Portulacaceae										
<i>Portulaca oleraceae</i> L.	0		n	0		0	10.3	± 3.3	mno	31
Onagraceae										
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	0		n	0		0	1.1	± 1.00		34
CV (%)	66.4			66.5			66.6			
LSD (0.1)	36.7			13.9			0.6			
LSD (0.5)	27.9			10.6			0.5			

^a Av of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P <0.01) by LSD statistical test.

^b survival (%) = $\frac{\text{Larvae pupating (no.)}}{\text{Total larvae (no.)}} \times 100$. ^c n = 10. ^d 1 = best, 34 = worst.

Table 2. Life history of *M. separata*.^a IIRRI greenhouse, May-Mar 1990.

	X ± SD	
Egg incubation (d)	3.0	± 0.4
Larval stadium (d)		
I	3.4	± 0.7
II	3.2	± 0.4
III	4.0	± 0.7
IV	4.4	± 0.5
V	4.9	± 0.3
Prepupa (d)	2.0	± 0
Pupa (d)	8.3	± 0.7
Total developmental period (d)	30.2	± 2.0
Moth longevity (d)	10.8	± 2.8
Eggs laid (no./female)	220.0	± 59.6

^a n = 10.

Integrated pest management — weeds

Weed species in rice seedling nurseries in Kafr El-Sheikh governorate, Egypt

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We surveyed weeds in farmers' rice seedling nurseries in Kafr El-Sheikh governorate in Egypt during 1992 summer season.

Twenty species belonging to 13 genera and 9 families were recorded in 30 nurseries. Grasses and broad-leaved weeds accounted for 74% of the species (see table). Those occurring most commonly were *Cyperus difformis*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Ammannia baccifera*, *E. colona*, *E. oryzoides*, and *Dinebra retroflexa*.

All of the farmers surveyed hand weeded the nurseries, achieving 50-70%

Weed species recorded in rice seedling nurseries in Kafr El-Sheikh governorate of Egypt. 1992 summer season.

Weed species	Family	Absolute presence ^a (n = 30)	Constancy ^b
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	28	0.93
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Poaceae	27	0.93
<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Lythraceae	24	0.80
<i>E. colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	21	0.70
<i>E. oryzoides</i> (Ard.) Fritsch.	Poaceae	17	0.5
<i>Dinebra retroflexa</i> (Vahl) Panzer	Poaceae	16	0.5
<i>Bergia capensis</i> L.	Elatinaceae	10	0.3
<i>Cyperus longus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	10	0.3
<i>E. phyllopogon</i> (Stapf.) Koss.	Poaceae	9	0.30
<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Poaceae	9	0.30
<i>A. multiflora</i> Roxb.	Lythraceae	9	0.30
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	8	0.27
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	Poaceae	8	0.27
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	7	0.23
<i>A. auriculata</i> Willd.	Lythraceae	7	0.23
<i>Lemna gibba</i> L.	Lemnaceae	6	0.20
<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	Asteraceae	5	0.17
<i>Lotus arabicus</i> L.	Fabaceae	4	0.13
<i>Chara</i> sp.	Characeae	3	0.10
<i>Azolla pinnata</i> R. Br.	Azollaceae	2	0.07

^aNumber of nurseries in which the species was recorded. ^bNumber of nurseries in which the species was recorded/total number of nurseries surveyed.

weed control. Hand weeding cannot control *Echinochloa* spp. due to their morphological similarities with rice seedlings; they are therefore transplanted with rice.

The farmers all pulled seedlings in bunches, along with the soil, to avoid making rice seedling bundles. This is another practice that results in transplanting rice and weeds, including *E. crus-galli*, *E. oryzoides*, *E. colona*, and *C. difformis*.

Between 5 and 30% of rice hills were infested with transplanted weeds, which are highly competitive with rice. ■

Farming systems

Slash-and-burn upland rice production in Bolivia's chapare region

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The chapare region of the Department of Cochabamba in Bolivia is located at the foot of the Andes in the Amazonian lowlands. Soils are acidic with pH of 4.0-5.5. Annual rainfall declines progressively from 5,000 mm in the southwest to 2,500 mm in the northeast. Bolivia has more than 120,000 ha of rice; all of it is upland on nonsloping land, and most is grown under mechanization on large farms. More than 15,000 ha are planted under slash-and-burn culture, however, which represents 6-10% of the country's total rice production of 225,000 t. About two-thirds of Bolivia's slash-and-burn

rice is planted in the chapare. Farmers have holdings of 5-50 ha. Lowland farm families consume an average 0.6-1.2 t milled rice per year. We interviewed 31 farmers from eight villages in Mar 1993 to describe the prevailing system of rice culture.

Rice is normally planted in Oct with the onset of the wet season. The forest is cleared from Jul to Sep during dry season. Farmers slash brush and fell trees (*chacear*), with time spent clearing depending on number of trees and average tree diameter. Virgin forests require a mean 36 d/ha to clear while regrowth (*chume*) requires a mean 26 d/ha. Brush and trees are left to dry for 1-2 mo before burning. Logs left after the first burn are piled for a second burning (9 d/ha).

On cleared virgin forest land, farmers usually plant two rice crops, followed by maize and/or cassava in the third year. The land is fallowed for an average of 7 yr before being returned to rice.

On the chume land, few soils are

sufficiently fertile for two consecutive rice crops. Land is left fallow for an average of 3 yr after cropping. In richer chume soils, banana follows the second year; in poorer soils, citrus and other fruits are planted. In the least fertile chume areas, rice is planted after clearing, and land is then fallowed for 3-7 yr before again planting rice.

Most popular cultivars are long-grained and about 1 m tall. Blue Bonnet was grown by 31% of the farmers during the 1992-93 season, followed by Pico Negro (23%), Carolina (22%), Blue Belle (8%), Cateto (8%), CICA8 (4%), Dominicana (2%), and Argentina (2%). Blue Bonnet, CICA8, Dominicana, and Argentina mature in 140 d, the others in 90 d. Farmers prefer later maturing cultivars for higher yield and earlier maturing ones to escape pests or for more immediate food consumption.

Seeds are planted in hills 25-40 cm apart using a dibble stick; on average, 9 seeds/hill are used. No purchased fertilizer is used. Virgin forest land